

Arteriovenous Fistula Associated with Pseudoaneurysm of the Tibioperoneal Trunk Secondary to Gunshot Wound Trauma: Case Report

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INTRODUCTION

Traumatic pseudoaneurysms and arteriovenous fistulas (AVFs) are recognized complications of penetrating vascular injuries. Although lower-extremity vascular trauma is relatively common in gunshot wounds, combined pseudoaneurysm and AVF of the tibioperoneal trunk is rare and may present in a delayed fashion.

In a collective review of 291 penetrating AVFs, 30% involved the lower extremities, and 44% were associated with pseudoaneurysms (1).

In a series of 60 gunshot-related AVFs of the lower limbs, 13% were located between the tibioperoneal trunk and posterior tibial veins; 55% had an associated pseudoaneurysm, and 40% developed complications such as distal arterial steal syndrome (2).

Popliteal and tibioperoneal pseudoaneurysms after gunshot trauma have been reported from 15 days up to 14 months after injury (3). Early recognition and appropriate intervention are essential to prevent limb-threatening complications including rupture, distal ischemia, and venous hypertension.

We present a case of tibioperoneal trunk pseudoaneurysm with associated AVF secondary to a gunshot wound, successfully managed with open surgical repair.

CASE REPORT

A 38-year-old male, with no relevant past medical history, presented to the emergency department with a two-month history of progressively increasing swelling in the right popliteal fossa, associated with pain and intermittent claudication, without having received prior medical treatment. Three months earlier, the patient had sustained a gunshot wound to the popliteal region. Additionally, he had a history of an open left tibial fracture, which was managed with external fixation at another institution.

On admission, the patient was hemodynamically stable, with vital signs within normal limits. Physical examination revealed localized swelling in the right popliteal fossa, with a palpable thrill and tenderness on palpation. Distal pulses were present, with no clinical evidence of active bleeding.

Laboratory studies showed no significant biochemical abnormalities, including hemoglobin 15 g/dL, leukocyte count $9.0 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, and hematocrit 45.0%.

A computed tomography angiography (CTA) was performed, demonstrating a pseudoaneurysm of the tibioperoneal trunk associated with an arteriovenous fistula, without evidence of active bleeding (Figure 1).

Based on these findings, a vascular surgery consultation was obtained, and surgical management was indicated. The patient underwent open surgical repair. Using a posterior popliteal approach, the popliteal artery was exposed and controlled. A pulsatile pseudoaneurysm measuring approximately 6–8 cm arising from the tibioperoneal trunk, with an associated arteriovenous fistula, was identified. The fistula was dismantled and repaired, followed by resection of the pseudoaneurysm. Vascular reconstruction was achieved using an autologous saphenous vein graft for arterial interposition. After reconstruction, adequate distal pulses were confirmed (Figures 2–5).

The postoperative course was uneventful. The patient exhibited a clean surgical wound, with no signs of infection, preserved distal pulses, and maintained range of motion.

Histopathological examination revealed an intramuscular capillary hemangioma in the left popliteal region, with an organizing thrombus.

The patient was discharged home with preserved distal perfusion. At follow-up, he remained asymptomatic, with adequate mobility and functional recovery of the affected limb.

Figure 1. (A) Computed tomography angiography (CTA) with three-dimensional vascular reconstruction demonstrating a pseudoaneurysm of the tibioperoneal trunk. (B) Sagittal CTA view showing the pseudoaneurysm arising from the tibioperoneal trunk.

Figure 2. Intraoperative view of the popliteal artery pseudoaneurysm, demonstrating a pulsatile mass consistent with associated arteriovenous fistula.

Figure 3. Intraoperative exposure of the distal and proximal ends of the tibioperoneal trunk after resection of the pseudoaneurysm and vascular control.

Figure 4. Interposition graft using autologous great saphenous vein between the popliteal artery and the tibioperoneal trunk following resection of the pseudoaneurysm and repair of the arteriovenous fistula.

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Figure 5. Resected pseudoaneurysm specimen following complete excision.

DISCUSSION

Traumatic AVFs and pseudoaneurysms of the lower extremity are uncommon but well documented after penetrating trauma (1,2). Gunshot injuries often damage adjacent arterial and venous structures simultaneously.

Clinical Presentation

Symptoms may include pulsatile mass, bruit, thrill, limb swelling, pain, venous hypertension, or distal ischemia. However, delayed presentations—even decades later—have been reported (3,4). Some patients remain minimally symptomatic for months or years (5,6).

Diagnosis

Doppler ultrasound and CTA are the primary diagnostic modalities (2,3,7). CTA allows precise vascular mapping and operative planning. Biphasic CT is particularly useful in detecting AVF flow dynamics in penetrating trauma (8).

Treatment

Management depends on hemodynamic stability and anatomical complexity.

Open Surgical Repair remains the gold standard in unstable patients or complex lesions. It includes pseudoaneurysm resection, AVF closure, and arterial reconstruction with autologous vein graft. Early intervention achieves high limb salvage rates (3,9).

Endovascular Treatment with covered stents or coil embolization has demonstrated favorable outcomes in tibial and peroneal arteries (10,11). These techniques allow exclusion of the pseudoaneurysm and closure of the AVF while preserving distal perfusion.

Hybrid Approaches combining open and endovascular techniques are described in giant or delayed pseudoaneurysms (12,13).

In our case, open repair was chosen due to anatomical considerations and the need for definitive AVF closure, with excellent functional outcome.

CONCLUSION

Pseudoaneurysm with AVF of the tibioperoneal trunk

secondary to gunshot trauma is rare but potentially limb-threatening. Delayed diagnosis is common. High clinical suspicion, early imaging with Doppler ultrasound and CTA, and timely repair—open or endovascular according to stability and anatomy—are essential to prevent distal arterial steal, venous hypertension, rupture, and limb loss.

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